

ANALYSIS OF NON-SYMMETRICAL THICK LAMINATED PLATES USING A VARIATIONAL APPROACH

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SUMMARY A new iterative theory based on a variational approach for the analysis of significantly non-homogeneous transversely isotropic plates of unsymmetrical structure is developed. The equilibrium equations, the relations between the generalised forces, and displacements, as well as, the boundary conditions were derived by using the Reissner variational principle. The proposed theory allows us, with a required accuracy and without major difficulties, to obtain solutions for different plate deformation problems. With the increase in the accuracy of the solution the order of the equations for the series of self-balanced stressed conditions remains constant and thus significantly simplifies the solutions with a high number of iterations. The analytical solutions are obtained for the bending problem of a simply supported plate and the results demonstrate a very good convergence and in a very good agreement with an exact three-dimensional solution.

KEYWORDS: Transversely isotropic plate; variational principle; iterative approach

INTRODUCTION

The use of laminated composite structures in various engineering applications, including such advanced fields like space and aircraft construction necessitated extensive studies and gave impetus to many publications in this field. The fundamental works by Ambartsumyan [1] and Lekhnitskii [2] substantially contributed to the development of the theory of anisotropic plates and shells. There is a demand for new efficient methods for the design of composite structures, which are increasingly used as primary structural elements. It is well known that to the heterogeneity of the materials of different layers the classical theory of plates, based on the Kirchoff-Love hypotheses, leads to substantial errors. The possibility of using a three-dimensional theory is of limited use due to mathematical difficulties and the complexity of the laminated system.

As a result, numerous theories of plates and shells have been formulated in recent years which approximate the three-dimensional solutions with reasonable accuracy. Such theories have been referred to as non-classical.

The beginning of the development of non-classical models links with the name of Timoshenko [3] who took into account the influence of the transverse shear deformations in

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the transverse vibrations of bars, and Reissner [4] for isotropic plates. The abandonment of Kirchoff-Love hypothesis (hypothesis of straight normal) and the use of the hypothesis of straight line allowed to take into account the influence of the transverse shear deformations, generalized through the thickness of the plate or the shell, homogeneous or laminated, as a refined factor.

One widely employed way to build hypotheses of the refined theories is to obtain the distribution law for the transverse shear stresses through the thickness of the layers by means of integration of the equilibrium equations of the 3D theory of the plate when the tangential normal stresses are given. For the heterogeneous laminated plates these laws became rather cumbersome. This difficulty was resolved by introducing the rational transverse shear deformation higher-order theory of laminated plates and shells [5]. A generalised plane-strain theory for transversely isotropic plates [6] was introduced by adopting an assumption that the through-the-thickness extensional strain is uniform through the plate thickness, and the three-dimensional governing equations were successfully reduced to the two coupled equations in the two-dimensional space. Other publications on the subject include a refined theory of transversely isotropic plates using Elliott-Lodge solutions and Lur'e operator method [7] and wave propagation and thermo-elasticity in the plate [8]. Assessment of shear deformation theories for multilayered composite plates by Noor and Burton [9] is worthy of notice.

In this study a new iterative theory based on a variational approach for significantly non-homogeneous laminated transversely isotropic plates is derived. This is further development of a methodology for the analysis of unsymmetrical thickness structure and end effects. The variation principle is based on works by Prusakov [10] and Plekhanov [11] and is referred to as the variation over a determining condition.

BASIC ASSUMPTIONS

We consider an elastic multilayered plate of constant thickness $h = h_1 + h_2$, made of an arbitrary number of transversely isotropic layers m with thicknesses t_k (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Geometry of a laminated plate.

The assumption that the layers are perfectly bonded ensures their deformation as a single unit without delamination. The coordinate surface is located at the distance h_1 from the

bottom surface of the plate, and the direction of the coordinate z is downwards. The position of the reference surface is determined according to the following condition

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E^{(k)}}{1 - \nu_k^2} \int_{t_k} z dz = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $E^{(k)}$ and $\nu^{(k)}$ are the elasticity moduli and Poisson's ratios in the plane of isotropy.

Since $z = h_1 - z_0$ we have for the k -th layer:

$$E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} z dz = -E_0^{(k)} \int_{d_{k-1}}^{d_k} (h_1 - z_0) dz_0 = -E_0^{(k)} t_k \left(h_1 - \frac{d_{k-1} + d_k}{2} \right)$$

After substitution of this expression in (1) we obtain

$$h_1 = \frac{1}{2} B^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} t_k (d_k + d_{k-1}) \quad (2)$$

where

$$E_0^{(k)} = \frac{E^{(k)}}{1 - \nu_k^2}; \quad B = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} t_k \quad (3)$$

We also assume that the external load is applied to the external surfaces of the plate as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } z = h_1 : \quad & \sigma_z = 0.5[q(x, y) - p(x, y)]; \quad \sigma_{xz} = \sigma_{yz} = 0 \\ \text{if } z = -h_2 : \quad & \sigma_z = -0.5[q(x, y) + p(x, y)]; \quad \sigma_{xz} = \sigma_{yz} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Taking into account the bonding conditions between the layers the expression for the displacements in the k -th layer for the laminated plate of non-symmetrical structure can be written to a first approximation as follows

$$\begin{aligned} u^{(k)} = (x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + z \frac{\partial w_1(x, y)}{\partial x} + (a_1^{(k)} + a_2^{(k)} z) u_1(x, y), \quad (u \rightarrow v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\ w^{(k)} &= w_1(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where u_0 and v_0 are the tangential displacements of the points on the coordinate surface. Constants $a_1^{(k)}$ and $a_2^{(k)}$ are determined from the boundary conditions at the interfaces for the tangential displacements and shear stresses according to the Hooke's law.

APPROXIMATION FUNCTIONS

We shall consider the deformations of laminated plate over the cylindrical surface. As a first approximation (non-self-balanced through the thickness) of the stress state we take

$$u = u_0 + z u^* + R^{(k)}(z) u_1 \quad (6)$$

Here $R^{(k)}$ is the function that takes the shear deformations into account and the second and the third items correspond to the bending deformations. At first we shall obtain the expressions for the transverse shear and normal stresses corresponded to the second item in (6). If the stress $\sigma_z^{(k)}$ is neglected, then

$$u^{(k)} = z u^*; \quad \varepsilon_x = \frac{du^{(k)}}{dx} = z \frac{du^*}{dx}; \quad \sigma_x^{(k)} = E_0^{(k)} \varepsilon_x = E_0^{(k)} z \frac{du^*}{dx} \quad (7)$$

Using the equilibrium equation

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x^{(k)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}^{(k)}}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (8)$$

we obtain

$$\sigma_{xz}^{(k)} = - \int \frac{\partial \sigma_x^{(k)}}{\partial x} dz + a_1^{(k)}(x) = -E_0^{(k)} \frac{d^2 u^*}{dx^2} \int z^2 dz + a_1^{(k)}(x) \quad (9)$$

In order to determine the constants $a_1^{(k)}$ we have $m - 1$ conditions of the rigid contact between the layers ($\sigma_{xz}^{(k)} = \sigma_{xz}^{(k+1)}$) and the two conditions on the external surfaces ($\sigma_{xz}^{(1)} = 0$ when $z = h_1$) and ($\sigma_{xz}^{(m)} = 0$ when $z = -h_2$). Thus there are the $m + 1$ conditions for the determination of a_1 .

The expressions for the transverse shear stresses, corresponding to the linear change of $u^{(k)}$ through the thickness is given by

$$\sigma_{xz}^{(k)} = -\frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} Q_x \int z dz + a_1^{(k)}(x) = \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} (a_1^{(k)} - z^2) Q_x \quad (10)$$

where

$$D_1 = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} z^2 dz; \quad Q_x = \frac{d}{dx} \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_x^{(k)} z dz; \quad (11)$$

The corresponding expression for the normal stresses $\sigma_z^{(k)}$ can be obtained by integrating the equilibrium equation

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_z^{(k)}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}^{(k)}}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (12)$$

over the thickness, and also together with equation (10):

$$\sigma_z^{(k)} = -\frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} (a_1^{(k)} z - z^3) \frac{dQ_x}{dx} + a_2^{(k)}(x) \quad (13)$$

Taking into account the symmetry of the load component p in (4) and substituting the derivative of the force Q_x by the load intensity $-q = dQ_x/dx$ the above expression can be simplified and written as

$$\sigma_z^{(k)} = -\frac{1}{2} p + \alpha_1^{(k)} q \quad (14)$$

where

$$\alpha_1^{(k)} = \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} (a_2^{(k)} - a_1^{(k)} z + z^3) \quad (15)$$

Here the constants $a_2^{(k)}$ are determined from $m - 1$ conditions at the layer interfaces ($\sigma_z^{(k)} = \sigma_z^{(k+1)}$) and load conditions at the external surfaces of the plate.

The expressions for $R^{(k)}(z)$ in (6) we obtain from equation (10) using the Hooke's law and assuming that $w = w(x)$

$$\frac{\partial u^{(k)}}{\partial z} = -\frac{dw}{dx} + \frac{\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}}{G_3^{(k)}} \quad (16)$$

where $G_3^{(k)}$ is the shear modulus in transverse direction. Substituting (10) into (16) and integrating over the thickness we obtain

$$u^{(k)} = -z \frac{dw}{dx} + R^{(k)} Q_x \quad (17)$$

where

$$R^{(k)} = \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1 G_3^{(k)}} (a_3^{(k)} + a_1^{(k)} z - z^3) \quad (18)$$

Because the linear law of the change of the tangential displacements through the thickness is already taken into account in (6), the first item in (17) is omitted in the further calculations. Now, according to (17) we shall derive the expressions for the transverse shear stresses by taking $\sigma_z^{(k)} = 0$ in the formula for $\sigma_x^{(k)}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x^{(k)} &= E_0^{(k)} \varepsilon_x = E_0^{(k)} R^{(k)}(z) \frac{dQ}{dx} \\ \sigma_{xz}^{*(k)} &= -\frac{d^2 Q_x}{dx^2} E_0^{(k)} \int R^{(k)}(z) dz + a_4^{(k)}(x) = f_*^{(k)} \frac{d^2 Q_x}{dx^2} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where

$$f_*^{(k)} = \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1 G_3^{(k)}} (a_4^{(k)} - a_3^{(k)} z - a_1^{(k)} z^2 + z^4) \quad (20)$$

Thus, in addition to the transverse shear stresses (10) which correspond to the second item in the expressions for the tangential displacements (6), the second item is obtained for the transverse shear stresses (19) and it corresponds to the third item of the tangential displacements (6).

Following the above procedure, the expressions for the displacements and stresses $\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}$, $\sigma_{yz}^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_z^{(k)}$ in the k -th layer take the form

$$\begin{aligned} u^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + zu^*(x, y) + R^{(k)}(z)u_1(x, y), \quad (u \rightarrow v, x \rightleftharpoons y) \\ w^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= w_1(x, y) \\ \sigma_{xz}^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= \frac{da_1^{(k)}(z)}{dz} Q_{1x}(x, y) + f_*^{(k)}(z) Q_x^*(x, y), \quad (x \rightarrow y) \\ \sigma_z^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= -0.5p(x, y) + \alpha_1(z)q(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

A version of the approximation (21) for the displacements $u^{(k)}$ has more independent varied functions. This increases the number of the tangential degrees of freedom of the laminated plate and allows us to describe more accurately, as a first approximation, the potential and rotational end effects. The presence of the two items in the expressions for the stresses $\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_{yz}^{(k)}$ allows us to determine more accurately the transverse shear stresses.

The approximation functions for the stresses $\sigma_x^{(k)}$, $\sigma_y^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_{xy}^{(k)}$ of the non-balanced condition through the thickness of the plate we shall obtain with the help of the Hooke's law and the Cauchy relations (21).

$$\sigma_x^{(k)} = E_0^{(k)} \left[\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + \nu^{(k)} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + z \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + \nu^{(k)} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} \right) \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + R^{(k)}(z) \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + \nu^{(k)} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} (1 + \nu^{(k)}) \sigma_z^{(k)} \Big] \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y, u \rightleftharpoons v) \\
\sigma_{xy}^{(k)} & = \frac{1}{2} E_0 (1 + \nu^{(k)}) \left[\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} + z \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) \right. \\
& \left. + R^{(k)}(z) \left(\frac{\partial u_1^{(k)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1^{(k)}}{\partial x} \right) \right] \tag{22}
\end{aligned}$$

The expressions for the next ($i \geq 2$) self-balanced stressed conditions contain polynomials $f_i(z)$ of the higher degree ($i + 2$) in the expressions for the displacements $u^{(k)}$, $v^{(k)}$, $w^{(k)}$ and stresses $\sigma_x^{(k)}$, $\sigma_y^{(k)}$, $\sigma_{xy}^{(k)}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
u^{(k)}(x, y, z) & = \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} f_i(z) u_i(x, y), \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y, u \rightarrow v) \\
w^{(k)}(x, y, z) & = \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{df_i(z)}{dz} w_i(x, y) \tag{23} \\
\sigma_x^{(k)}(x, y, z) & = \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} f_i M_{ix}(x, y) \quad (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy)
\end{aligned}$$

where a second and a third approximations are

$$\begin{aligned}
f_2 & = h(b_3 + b_4 z + b_5 z^2 + b_6 z^4) \\
f_3 & = c_3 + c_4 z + c_5 z^2 + c_6 z^3 + c_7 z^5 \tag{24}
\end{aligned}$$

The polynomial constants are determined from the following conditions of orthogonality

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{ix}^{(k)} u_{(i-1)}^{(k)} dz = 0 \tag{25}$$

It follows from (25) that the constants b_4 , c_3 and c_5 become equal zero if the plate has a symmetrical structure through the thickness. As a result we get the two systems of the functions describing both the symmetrical and asymmetrical bending deformations. The final self-balanced transverse shear and normal stresses can be obtained by integrating the equilibrium equations (8)

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{xz}^{(k)} & = \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{d\alpha_i^{(k)}(z)}{dz} Q_{ix}(x, y) \\
\sigma_z^{(k)} & = - \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \alpha_i^{(k)}(z) \omega_i(x, y) \tag{26}
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_2^{(k)} & = - \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} (b_1^{(k)} + b_2^{(k)} z + b_3 z^2 + b_4 z^3 + b_5 z^4 + b_6 z^6) \\
\alpha_3^{(k)} & = - \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} (c_1^{(k)} + c_2^{(k)} z + c_3 z^2 + c_4 z^3 + c_5 z^4 + c_6 z^6 + c_7 z^7), \dots \tag{27}
\end{aligned}$$

The polynomials $\alpha_i^{(k)}$ ($i > 3$), used in the expressions for the stresses $\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}$, $\sigma_{yz}^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_z^{(k)}$ for the subsequent self-balanced stressed states are built analogously to $\alpha_2^{(k)}$ and $\alpha_3^{(k)}$.

The functions f_i for the approximation of the displacements $u^{(k)}$, $v^{(k)}$ and $w^{(k)}$ and stresses $\sigma_x^{(k)}$, $\sigma_y^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_{xy}^{(k)}$ for the each subsequent approximation ($i > 3$) must have by one term more than the previous one. In this case, the order of the polynomial f_i in the next approximation is higher than the order of f_{i-1} . The polynomial constants are determined from the orthogonality condition of the tangential stress terms of the subsequent stress states to the previous tangential displacements.

The derivation of the polynomials of the second f_2 and third f_3 order in [11] was done separately for the symmetrical and asymmetrical bending deformations of the plate. The refinement of the solution of problems using these functions was done for the plates with the ratios of the elasticity moduli of the layers ≤ 100 . The increase of the order of the polynomials f_2 and f_3 by two comparing to [11] has improved the convergence in the subsequent approximations for significantly non-homogeneous plates. Thus, the following approximation functions for the displacements and stresses of the first and subsequent stress states are used here

$$\begin{aligned}
u^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y) + zu^*(x, y) + R^{(k)}(z)u_1(x, y) + \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} f_i(z)u_i(x, y) \quad (u \rightarrow v, x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
w^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= w_1(x, y) + \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{df_i(z)}{dz} w_i(x, y); \\
\sigma_x^{(k)}(x, y) &= E_0^{(k)} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + \nu^{(k)} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + z \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + \nu^{(k)} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} \right) R^{(k)}(z) \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + \nu^{(k)} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} (1 + \nu^{(k)}) [-0.5p(x, y) + \alpha_1^{(k)}(z)q(x, y)] \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} f_i(z) M_{ix}(x, y) \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v, x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
\sigma_{x,y}^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= 0.5E_0^{(k)}(1 + \nu^{(k)}) \left[\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} + z \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + R^{(k)}(z) \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right) \right] + \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} f_i(z) M_{ixy}(x, y) \\
\sigma_{x,z}^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= \frac{d\alpha_1^{(k)}(z)}{dz} Q_{1x}(x, y) + f_*^{(k)} Q_x^*(x, y) + \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{d\alpha_i^{(k)}(z)}{dz} Q_{ix} \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
\sigma_z^{(k)}(x, y, z) &= -0.5p(x, y) + \alpha_1^{(k)}(z)q(x, y) - \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \alpha_i^{(k)}(z)\omega_i(x, y)
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

Here, for the expansion over the thickness coordinate z the following polynomials are used: $\alpha_1^{(k)}$ in line with the expression (15), $f_*^{(k)}$ – (20) and $R^{(k)}$ – (18) for the non-balanced stress state, and f_i – (24), $\alpha_i^{(k)}$ – (27) for the subsequent ($i = 2, 3$) self-balanced stress states.

The constants $a_1^{(k)}, \dots, a_4^{(k)}$ used in the expressions for $\alpha_1^{(k)}$, $f_*^{(k)}$ and $R^{(k)}$ as a first approximation are determined from the solution of the following equations

$$\sigma_{1xz}^{(1)} = 0, \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow \frac{d\alpha_1^{(k)}}{dz} = 0;$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{1xz}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{1xz}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow \frac{d\alpha_1^{(k)}}{dz} = \frac{d\alpha_1^{(k+1)}}{dz} \\
\sigma_{1z}^{(1)}(q) &= 0.5q \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow \alpha_1^{(k)} = 0.5 \\
\sigma_{1z}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{1z}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow \alpha_1^{(k)} = \alpha_1^{(k+1)} \\
u_{(1)}^{(k)} &= u_{(1)}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow R^{(k)} = R^{(k+1)} \\
\sigma_{1xz}^{*(1)} &= 0 \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow f_*^{(1)} = 0 \\
\sigma_{1xz}^{*(m)} &= 0 \quad \text{if } z = -h_2 \longrightarrow f_*^{(m)} = 0 \\
\sigma_{1xz}^{*(k)} &= \sigma_{1xz}^{*(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow f_*^{(k)} = f_*^{(k+1)}
\end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

where $H_k = h_1 - d_k$.

The constants b_3, \dots, b_6 used in the expressions for f_2 are determined from the conditions of orthogonality of the tangential stresses and displacements as follows

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{2xz}^{(k)} u_{(1)}^{(k)} dz = 0 \tag{30}$$

and also from the condition that $f_2 = 1$ when $z = h_1$. The values of $b_1^{(k)}$ and $b_2^{(k)}$ we obtain from the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{2xz}^{(1)} &= 0, \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow \frac{d\alpha_2^{(k)}}{dz} = 0; \\
\sigma_{2xz}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{2xz}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow \frac{d\alpha_2^{(k)}}{dz} = \frac{d\alpha_2^{(k+1)}}{dz} \\
\sigma_{2z}^{(1)} &= 0 \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow \alpha_2^{(1)} = 0 \\
\sigma_{2z}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{2z}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow \alpha_2^{(k)} = \alpha_2^{(k+1)}
\end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

The constants c_3, \dots, c_7 which are used in the expressions for $f_3(z)$ (24) can be determined from the following orthogonality conditions

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{3xz}^{(k)} u_{(1)}^{(k)} dz = 0; \quad \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{3xz}^{(k)} u_{(2)}^{(k)} dz = 0 \tag{32}$$

and from the condition that $f_3 = 1$ when $z = h_1$.

The values of $c_1^{(k)}$ and $c_2^{(k)}$ used in the expressions for $\alpha_3^{(k)}$ (27) we determine from the conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{3xz}^{(1)} &= 0 \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow \frac{d\alpha_3^{(1)}}{dz} = 0 \\
\sigma_{3xz}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{3xz}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow \frac{d\alpha_3^{(k)}}{dz} = \frac{d\alpha_3^{(k+1)}}{dz} \\
\sigma_{3z}^{(1)} &= 0 \quad \text{if } z = h_1 \longrightarrow \alpha_3^{(1)} = 0 \\
\sigma_{3z}^{(k)} &= \sigma_{3z}^{(k+1)} (k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1) \quad \text{if } z = H_k \longrightarrow \alpha_3^{(k)} = \alpha_3^{(k+1)}
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

The proposed variant of the approximation functions for the displacements and stresses describe with a high degree of accuracy the stress-strain state of the laminated plates under the influence of both distributed and local forces.

VARIATIONAL EQUATION FOR LAMINATED PLATES

In order to obtain the governing equations of bending, the boundary conditions and the relations of elasticity, we will use the mixed Reissner's variational principle, which has the following form for the transversely isotropic layered plate

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta R = & \iint \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \left\{ \sigma_x^{(k)} \delta \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \sigma_y^{(k)} \delta \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \sigma_z^{(k)} \delta \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} + \sigma_{xy}^{(k)} \delta \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \right. \\
& + \sigma_{xz}^{(k)} \delta \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) + \sigma_{yz}^{(k)} \delta \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) \\
& + \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{E^{(k)}} \left(\sigma_x^{(k)} - \nu^{(k)} \sigma_y^{(k)} + \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} \sigma_z^{(k)} \right) \right] \delta \sigma_x^{(k)} \\
& + \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{1}{E^{(k)}} \left(\sigma_y^{(k)} - \nu^{(k)} \sigma_x^{(k)} + \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} \sigma_z^{(k)} \right) \right] \delta \sigma_y^{(k)} \\
& + \left[\frac{\partial w}{\partial z} - \frac{1}{E^{(k)}} \left(\sigma_z^{(k)} - \nu_3^{(k)} (\sigma_x^{(k)} + \sigma_y^{(k)}) \right) \right] \delta \sigma_z^{(k)} \\
& + \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{2(1 + \nu^{(k)})}{E^{(k)}} \sigma_{xy}^{(k)} \right] \delta \sigma_{xy}^{(k)} \\
& + \left. \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} - \frac{\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}}{G_3^{(k)}} \right) \delta \sigma_{xz}^{(k)} + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} - \frac{\sigma_{yz}^{(k)}}{G_3^{(k)}} \right) \delta \sigma_{yz}^{(k)} \right\} dx dy dz \\
& - \iint_A (X \delta u + Y \delta v + Z \delta w) dA = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

Here $X, Y,$ and Z are external forces applied to the surface of the plate. By varying the above equation with respect to the displacements we obtain the equilibrium equations and the boundary conditions, and the variation over the stresses gives us the elasticity relations. If the standard variation method is used in (34) the order of the main differential equations will be increasing with the number of items in the approximation functions for the stresses and displacements. Such equations are called tied and the increase of the order of the equations makes the computation significantly difficult, whereas a small number of the items in the functions leads to an insufficient accuracy. This difficulty may be obviated by using the variation over the determining condition proposed in [10,11]. This method allows us to obtain instead of a system of equations, a sequence of separate groups of equations, the order of which will be independent of the total number of the items in the functions.

First, we substitute the derived expressions for the stresses and displacements in (34) and integrate with respect to z . For the first condition ($i = 0, 1$), after the integration by parts, we have:

$$\iint \left[\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} \delta u_0 + \frac{\partial M_{1x}}{\partial x} \delta u^* + \frac{\partial \tilde{M}_{1x}}{\partial x} \delta u_1 + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} \delta v_0 + \frac{\partial M_{1y}}{\partial y} \delta v^* \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\partial \tilde{M}_{1y}}{\partial y} \delta v_1 + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} \delta u_0 + \frac{\partial M_{1xy}}{\partial y} \delta u^* + \frac{\partial \tilde{M}_{1xy}}{\partial y} \delta u_1 + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial x} \delta v_0 \\
& + \frac{\partial M_{1xy}}{\partial x} \delta v^* + \frac{\partial \tilde{M}_{1xy}}{\partial x} \delta v_1 - L_{4111} Q_x^* \delta u^* - L_{4311} Q_x^* \delta u_1 \\
& - L_{1111} Q_{1x} \delta u^* - L_{3811} Q_{1x} \delta u_1 - L_{4111} Q_y^* \delta v^* - L_{4311} Q_y^* \delta v_1 \\
& - L_{1111} Q_{1y} \delta v^* - L_{3811} Q_{1y} \delta v_1 + L_{4111} \left(\frac{\partial Q_x^*}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y^*}{\partial y} \right) \delta w_1 \\
& - L_{1111} \left(\frac{\partial Q_{1x}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{1y}}{\partial y} \right) \delta w_1 - q \delta w_1 \Big] dx dy - \int [N_x \delta u_0 + M_{1x} \delta u^* \\
& + \tilde{M}_{1x} \delta u_1 + N_{xy} \delta v_0 + M_{1xy} \delta v^* + \tilde{M}_{1xy} \delta v_1 + (L_{4111} Q_x^* + L_{1111} Q_{1x}) \delta w_1] dy \\
& - \int [N_y \delta v_0 + N_{xy} \delta u_0 + M_{1y} \delta v^* + M_{1xy} \delta u^* + \tilde{M}_{1y} \delta v_1 \\
& + \tilde{M}_{1xy} \delta u_1 + L_{4111} Q_y^* \delta w_1 + L_{1111} Q_{1y}) \delta w_1] dx \tag{35} \\
& + \iint \left[\left(L_{1111} u^* + L_{1111} \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} + L_{3811} u_1 - L_{1211} Q_{1x} - L_{4211} Q_x^* \right) \delta Q_{1x} \right. \\
& + \left(L_{4111} u^* + L_{4111} \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} + L_{4311} u_1 - L_{4211} Q_{1x} - L_{4411} Q_x^* \right) \delta Q_x^* \\
& + \left(L_{1111} v^* + L_{1111} \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} + L_{3811} v_1 - L_{1211} Q_{1y} - L_{4211} Q_y^* \right) \delta Q_{1y} \\
& + \left. \left(L_{4111} v^* + L_{4111} \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} + L_{4311} v_1 - L_{4211} Q_{1y} - L_{4411} Q_y^* \right) \delta Q_y^* \right] dx dy \\
& - \int_{\Omega_1} [\bar{N}_x \delta u_0 + \bar{N}_{yx} \delta v_0 + \bar{M}_{1x} \delta u^* + \bar{M}_{1x} \delta u_1 + \bar{M}_{xy} \delta v^* \\
& + \bar{M}_{xy} \delta v_1 + \bar{Q}_{1x} \delta w_1] dy - \int_{\Omega_2} [\bar{N}_y \delta v_0 + \bar{N}_{xy} \delta u_0 \\
& + \bar{M}_{1y} \delta v^* + \bar{M}_{1y} \delta v_1 + \bar{M}_{xy} \delta u_1 + \bar{M}_{xy} \delta u^* + \bar{Q}_{1y} \delta w_1] dx = 0
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
N_x &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy) \\
M_{1x} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} z dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy) \\
\tilde{M}_{1x} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} R^{(k)}(z) dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy) \\
\bar{N}_x &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} p_x dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy)
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{M}_{jx} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} p_x f_j dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy) \\ \bar{M}_{1x} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} p_x R^{(k)} dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy) \\ \bar{Q}_{jx} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} p_{zx} \frac{df_i}{dz} dz & (x \rightarrow y)\end{aligned}$$

Here p_x, p_y, p_{zx}, p_{zy} and p_{xy} are load components applied to the plate (see Figure 2.). In (35) and in the next derivations, two last digits in the coefficients L are indices of the integrand, and two preceding ones represent the number of the coefficient (see Appendix A).

The variation equation for $j \geq 2$ is written similar to (35):

$$\begin{aligned}& \iint \left[\frac{\partial M_{jx}^*}{\partial x} \delta u_j + \frac{\partial M_{jy}^*}{\partial y} \delta v_j + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{1ij} \left(\frac{\partial M_{ix}}{\partial x} \delta u_j + \frac{\partial M_{iy}}{\partial y} \delta v_j \right) \right. \\ & + \frac{\partial M_{jxy}^*}{\partial x} \delta v_j + \frac{\partial M_{jyx}^*}{\partial y} \delta u_j + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{1ij} \left(\frac{\partial M_{ixy}}{\partial x} \delta v_j + \frac{\partial M_{ixy}}{\partial y} \delta u_j \right) \\ & + L_{411j} \left(\frac{\partial Q_x^*}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y^*}{\partial y} \right) \delta w_j + \sum_{i=1}^j L_{3ij} \left(\frac{\partial Q_{ix}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{iy}}{\partial y} \right) \delta w_j \\ & - L_{411j} (Q_x^* \delta u_j + Q_y^* \delta v_j) - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{3ij} (Q_{ix} \delta u_j + Q_{iy} \delta v_j) \\ & - \left(L_{21j} q - 0.5 L_{20j} p - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{2ij} \omega_i \right) \delta w_j + 0.5 (F_{1j} q - F_{2j} p) \delta w_j \left. \right] dx dy \\ & - \int \left[M_{jx}^* \delta u_j + M_{jxy}^* \delta v_j + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{1ij} (M_{ix} \delta u_j + M_{ixy} \delta v_j) \right. \\ & + \left. \left(L_{11j} Q_x^* + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{3ij} Q_{ix} \right) \delta w_j \right] dy - \int [M_{iy}^* \delta v_j + M_{jxy}^* \delta u_j \\ & + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{12j} (M_{iy} \delta v_j + M_{ixy} \delta u_j) + \left(L_{411j} Q_y^* + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{3ij} Q_{iy} \right) \delta w_j] dx \\ & + \iint \left\{ \left(U_{jx} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{1ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} - S_{jx} - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{4ij} M_{ix} + S_{jy}^* + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{5ij} M_{iy} \right. \right. \\ & - L_{60j} 0.5 p + L_{61j} q - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{6ij} \omega_i \left. \right) \delta M_{jx} + \left(V_{jy} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{1ij} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y} \right. \\ & + \left. S_{jx}^* + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{5ij} M_{ix} - S_{jy} - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{4ij} M_{iy} - L_{60j} 0.5 p - L_{61j} q \right. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{6ij} \omega_i \Big) \delta M_{jy} + \left[U_{jy} + V_{jx} - T_j + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{1ij} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x} \right) \right. \\
& - 2L_{7ij} M_{ixy} \Big] \delta M_{jxy} - \left[\sum_{i=1}^j L_{8ij} w_i + L_{90j} 0.5p - L_{91j} q \right. \\
& + \left. \sum_{i=2}^j L_{9ij} \omega_i + S_{3jx} + S_{3jy} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{10ij} (M_{ix} + M_{iy}) \right] \delta \omega_j \\
& + \left(\sum_{i=1}^j L_{11ij} \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial x} + U_{3j} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{11ij} u_i - \sum_{i=1}^j L_{12ij} Q_{ix} - L_{411j} Q_x^* \right) \delta Q_{jx} \\
& + \left(\sum_{i=1}^j L_{11ij} \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial y} + V_{3j} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{11ij} v_i - \sum_{i=1}^j L_{12ij} Q_{iy} - L_{411j} Q_y^* \right) \delta Q_{jy} \Big\} dx dy \\
& - \int_{\Omega_1} (\bar{M}_{jx} \delta u_j + \bar{M}_{jyx} \delta v_j + \bar{Q}_{jx} \delta w_j) dy - \int_{\Omega_2} (\bar{M}_{jy} \delta v_j + \bar{M}_{jxy} \delta u_j + \bar{Q}_{jy} \delta w_j) dx = 0
\end{aligned}$$

The following notations are used in the above equation

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{jx}^* &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} f_j dz & (x \rightarrow y, x \rightarrow xy) \\
S_{jx}^* &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu^{(k)} E_0^{(k)}}{E^{(k)} D_1} \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} f_j dz & (x \rightarrow y) \\
S_{jx} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{E^{(k)} D_1} \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} f_j dz & (x \rightarrow y) \\
S_{3jx} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1x}^{(k)} \alpha_i dz & (x \rightarrow y) \\
U_{jx} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \int_{t_k} \frac{\partial u_1^{(k)}}{\partial x} f_j dz & (x \rightarrow y) \\
V_{jx} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \int_{t_k} \frac{\partial v_1^{(k)}}{\partial x} f_j dz & (x \rightarrow y) \\
U_{3j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \frac{\partial u_1^{(k)}}{\partial z} \frac{d\alpha_j^{(k)}}{dz} dz \\
V_{3j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \frac{\partial v_1^{(k)}}{\partial z} \frac{d\alpha_j^{(k)}}{dz} dz \\
T_j &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{G^{(k)}} \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \int_{t_k} \sigma_{1xy}^{(k)} f_j dz \\
F_{1j} &= \frac{\partial f_j}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=h_1} + \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=-h_2}
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

$$F_{2j} = \frac{\partial f_j}{\partial z (z=h_1)} - \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial z (z=-h_2)}$$

Figure 2. Load components on the lateral surfaces of the plate.

EQUILIBRIUM EQUATIONS AND GENERALISED FORCES

The variations of independent functions $u_0, u_1, u^*, v_0, v_1, v^*, w_1$ in (35) and u_j, v_j and w_j in (37), which determine the displacements in the plate, have arbitrary values everywhere over the domain of the plate excluding the boundary, and consequently they cannot be equal to zero. Equating the multipliers of the variations in the integrals to zero, we obtain the system of equations of equilibrium of the plate in the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} &= 0 \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y) \\ \frac{\partial M_{1x}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_{1xy}}{\partial y} - L_{311}Q_{1x} - L_{4111}Q_x^* &= 0 \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y) \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{M}_{1x}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tilde{M}_{1xy}}{\partial y} - L_{3811}Q_{1x} - L_{4311}Q_x^* &= 0 \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y) \\ L_{311} \left(\frac{\partial Q_{1x}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{1y}}{\partial y} \right) + L_{4111} \left(\frac{\partial Q_x^*}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y^*}{\partial y} \right) &= -q \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

And for $j \geq 2$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& L_{1jj} \left(\frac{\partial M_{jx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_{jxy}}{\partial y} \right) - L_{3jj} Q_{jx} = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} L_{3ij} Q_{ix} \\
& + L_{411j} Q_x^* - \frac{\partial M_{jx}^*}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M_{jxy}^*}{\partial y} \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y) \tag{40} \\
& L_{3jj} \left(\frac{\partial Q_{jx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{jy}}{\partial y} \right) + L_{2jj} \omega_j = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} L_{3ij} Q_{ix} \left(\frac{\partial Q_{ix}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{iy}}{\partial y} \right) \\
& - L_{411j} \left(\frac{\partial Q_x^*}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y^*}{\partial y} \right) - \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} L_{2ij} \omega_i + L_{21j} q - 0.5 L_{20j} p - 0.5 (F_{1j} - F_{2j} p)
\end{aligned}$$

Varying over Q_{1x} , Q_{1y} , Q_x^* and Q_y^* in equation (35) we can write down the elasticity relations and obtain these forces as

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{1x} &= a_{4011}^{-1} \left[a_{3611} \left(\frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} + u^* \right) + a_{3711} u_1 \right] \quad (x \rightarrow y) \\
Q_x^* &= a_{4011}^{-1} \left[a_{3811} \left(\frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} + u^* \right) + a_{3911} u_1 \right] \quad (x \rightarrow y) \tag{41}
\end{aligned}$$

Where a coefficients represent some combinations of the L coefficients (see Appendix B).

The rest of the elasticity relations can be derived by substituting the expressions for the stresses in (36) and integrating over z through the thickness

$$\begin{aligned}
N_x &= B \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + L_{1700} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + B_1 \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + L_{1710} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} + L_{1810} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} \\
&+ L_{1910} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} - L_{2000} 0.5p + L_{2010} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
N_{xy} &= 0.5 \left[L_{1400} \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right) + L_{1410} \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) + L_{1510} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right) \right] \\
M_{1x} &= B_1 \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + L_{1710} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + D_1 \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + L_{1711} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} + L_{1811} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} \\
&+ L_{1911} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} - L_{2010} 0.5p + L_{2011} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \tag{42} \\
M_{1xy} &= 0.5 \left[L_{1410} \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right) + L_{1411} \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) + L_{1511} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right) \right] \\
\tilde{M}_{1x} &= L_{1810} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + L_{1910} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + L_{1811} \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + L_{1911} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} + L_{3911} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} \\
&+ L_{4011} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} - L_{1610} 0.5p + L_{1611} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
\tilde{M}_{1xy} &= 0.5 \left[L_{1510} \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right) + L_{1511} \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) + L_{4511} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

After substituting the approximation functions for the stresses and displacements into (38) and integrating over the thickness we obtain the following relations

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{jx}^* &= L_{170j} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + L_{171j} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} + L_{181j} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + L_{191j} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} \\
&\quad - L_{2000} 0.5p + L_{201j} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
M_{jxy}^* &= -0.5 \left[L_{170j} \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right) + L_{171j} \left(\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) + L_{151j} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right) \right] \\
S_{jx} &= D_1 \left(L_{40j} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + L_{41j} \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + L_{50j} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + L_{51j} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} \right) \\
&\quad + L_{261j} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + L_{271j} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} - L_{280j} 0.5p + L_{281j} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
S_{jx}^* &= D_1 \left(L_{50j} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + L_{51j} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial x} \right) + L_{290j} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + L_{291j} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} \\
&\quad + L_{301j} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + L_{311j} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} - L_{320j} 0.5p + L_{321j} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
S_{3jx} &= D_1 L_{100j} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + L_{330j} \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + D_1 L_{101j} \frac{\partial u^*}{\partial x} + L_{331j} \frac{\partial v^*}{\partial y} \\
&\quad + L_{341j} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + L_{351j} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} - L_{360j} 0.5p + L_{361j} q \quad (u \rightleftharpoons v; x \rightleftharpoons y) \\
U_{3j} &= L_{371j} u_1; \quad V_{3j} = L_{371j} v_1; \quad T_j = 0 \\
U_{jx} &= \frac{L_{181j}}{D_1} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x}; \quad V_{jx} = \frac{L_{181j}}{D_1} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y)
\end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

And lastly, equating the variations to zero in (37) we obtain the expressions for the condition where $j \geq 2$:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{jx} &= \frac{1}{L_{7jj} L_{13jj}} \left\{ L_{4jj} \left[U_{jx} + L_{1jj} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x} - S_{jx} - S_{jy}^* - 0.5 L_{60j} p \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + L_{61j} q - L_{6jj} \omega_j - \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} (L_{4ij} M_{ix} - L_{5ij} M_{iy} + L_{6ij} \omega_i) \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + L_{5jj} \left[V_{jy} + L_{1jj} \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial y} + S_{jx}^* - S_{jy} - 0.5 L_{60j} p + L_{61j} q \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} (L_{4ij} M_{iy} - L_{5ij} M_{ix} + L_{6ij} \omega_i) \right] \right\} \\
M_{jy} &= \frac{1}{L_{7jj} L_{13jj}} \left\{ L_{5jj} \left[U_{jx} + L_{1jj} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x} - S_{jx} + S_{jy}^* - 0.5 L_{60j} p \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + L_{61j} q - L_{6jj} \omega_j - \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} (L_{4ij} M_{ix} - L_{5ij} M_{iy} + L_{6ij} \omega_i) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + L_{4jj} \left[V_{jy} + L_{1jj} \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial y} + S_{jx}^* - S_{jy} - 0.5L_{60j}p + L_{61j}q \right. \\
& \left. - \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} (L_{4ij}M_{iy} - L_{51j}M_{ix} + L_{6ij}\omega_i) \right] \\
M_{jxy} & = \frac{1}{2L_{7jj}} \left[-2 \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} L_{7ij}M_{ixy} + L_{1jj} \left(\frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial y} \right) - T_j - U_{jy} - V_{jx} \right] \\
Q_{jx} & = \frac{1}{L_{12jj}} \left[U_{3j} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{11ij} \left(\frac{\partial w_i}{\partial x} + u_i \right) - \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} L_{12ij}Q_{ix} - L_{441j}Q_x^* \right] \\
Q_{jy} & = \frac{1}{L_{12jj}} \left[V_{3j} + \sum_{i=2}^j L_{11ij} \left(\frac{\partial w_i}{\partial y} + v_i \right) - \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} L_{12ij}Q_{iy} - L_{441j}Q_y^* \right] \\
\omega_j & = \frac{1}{L_{9jj}} \left[- \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} L_{9ij}\omega_i - S_{3jx} - S_{3jy} - \sum_{i=2}^j L_{10ij}(M_{ix} + M_{iy}) \right. \\
& \left. - \sum_{i=1}^j L_{8ij}w_i - 0.5L_{90j}p + L_{91j}q \right] \tag{45}
\end{aligned}$$

It is significant that for the plates with the symmetrical structure of the layers through the thickness the expressions for the moments M_{jx} , M_{jy} and M_{jxy} become much simpler since they do not contain the forces from the previous stress conditions. Different variants of the boundary conditions are obtained from the line integrals in the variational equations (35) and (37). For the plate edge, coinciding with the coordinate line $x = \text{const}$ we have the first stress condition ($i = 0, 1$)

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The stress state of a laminated plate, likewise of a homogeneous one, consists of the internal stress state, potential and vortical end effects. The internal stress state is distributed over the entire plate. The stress state in the boundary layer has a local character and is localized close to the edges and other lines of disturbance (ribs, pointed loads, holes and so on). There are potential and vortical boundary layers. In order to derive the equations which describe the vortical and potential boundary layers as well as the internal stress state we substitute the elasticity relations (41), (42)-(44) into (39) and (40). The first group of the equations can be given as follows

$$L_{1400} \nabla^2 \psi_0 + L_{1410} \nabla^2 \psi_* + L_{1510} \nabla^2 \psi_1 = 0 \tag{46}$$

$$L_{1410} \nabla^2 \psi_0 + L_{1411} \nabla^2 \psi_* + L_{1511} \nabla^2 \psi_1 + 2(a_{4111}\psi_* + a_{4211}\psi_1) = 0 \tag{47}$$

$$L_{1510} \nabla^2 \psi_0 + L_{1511} \nabla^2 \psi_* + L_{4511} \nabla^2 \psi_1 + 2(a_{4311}\psi_* + a_{4411}\psi_1) = 0 \tag{48}$$

Where

$$\psi_i = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x}$$

Here the equation (46) is auxiliary and in the subsequent derivations the coefficient ψ_0

will be excluded from (47) and (48) with the help of it, and they will be describing the vortical effect.

The second group of the equations is given by

$$B \nabla^2 \varphi_0 + B_1 \nabla^2 \varphi_* + L_{1810} \nabla^2 \varphi_1 - 0.5L_{2000} \nabla^2 p + L_{2010} \nabla^2 q = 0 \quad (49)$$

$$B_1 \nabla^2 \varphi_0 + D_1 \nabla^2 \varphi_* + L_{1811} \nabla^2 \varphi_1 - 0.5L_{2010} \nabla^2 p + L_{2011} \nabla^2 q + a_{4111}(\nabla^2 w_1 + \varphi_*) + a_{4211} \varphi_1 = 0 \quad (50)$$

$$L_{1810} \nabla^2 \varphi_0 + L_{1811} \nabla^2 \varphi_* + L_{3911} \nabla^2 \varphi_1 - 0.5L_{1610} \nabla^2 p + L_{1611} \nabla^2 q + a_{4311}(\nabla^2 w_1 + \varphi_*) + a_{4411} \varphi_1 = 0 \quad (51)$$

$$a_{4111}(\nabla^2 w_1 + \varphi_*) + a_{4211} \varphi_1 = q \quad (52)$$

where

$$\varphi_i = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y}$$

Here the equation (49) is auxiliary and will be employed in the subsequent derivations to exclude the coefficients φ_0 from (50) and (51). The equations (50)-(52) describe the internal stress state and the potential effect.

The self-balanced condition $j \geq 2$ is also represented by the two equations. The first equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \nabla^2 \psi_j - a_{24jj} \psi_j = -\frac{L_{181j}}{D_1 L_{1jj}} \nabla^2 \psi_1 + a_{261j} a_{22jj} \psi_1 \\ & - a_{22jj} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} (M_{jx}^* - M_{jy}) - \frac{\partial^2 M_{jxy}^*}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 M_{jxy}^*}{\partial y^2} \right] \\ & + \frac{1}{L_{1jj}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} (S_{jx} - S_{jy} + S_{jx}^* - S_{jy}^*) + \frac{L_{371j}}{L_{1jj}} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) \\ & \times \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right) + a_{251j} a_{22jj} \left(\frac{\partial Q_x^*}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial Q_y^*}{\partial x} \right) \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} a_{23ij} \left(\frac{\partial Q_{ix}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial Q_{iy}}{\partial x} \right) + \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} \{ a_{24ij} \psi_i \\ & + L_{1jj} a_{22ij} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} (M_{ix} - M_{iy}) + \frac{\partial^2 M_{ixy}}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 M_{ixy}}{\partial x^2} \right] \} \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

describes the vortical effect.

The second equation refines the internal stress state and describes the potential end effect.

$$\begin{aligned} & a_{13jj} a_{15jj} \nabla^4 w_j - a_{17jj} \nabla^2 w_j + a_{14jj} L_{8jj} w_j \\ & = 0.5 a_{20jj} (a_{40j} - F_{2j}) p + 0.5 a_{20jj} F_{1j} q - (0.5 a_{180j} - a_{15jj} F_{2j}) \nabla^2 p + a_{331j} \psi_1 \\ & - 0.5 a_{15jj} F_{1j} \nabla^2 q - a_{321j} \nabla^2 \varphi_1 + a_{251j} (a_{21jj} - a_{15jj} \nabla^2) \left(\frac{\partial Q_x^*}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_y^*}{\partial y} \right) + S_{8j} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \left[a_{20jj} a_{4ij} \omega_i - a_{18ij} \nabla^2 \omega_i - a_{15jj} a_{13ij} \nabla^4 w_i \right] \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + a_{17ij} \nabla^2 w_i - a_{14jj} L_{8ij} w_i + a_{9ij} (a_{21jj} - a_{15jj} \nabla^2) \\
& \times \left(\frac{\partial Q_{ix}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_{iy}}{\partial y} \right) + \sum_{i=2}^{j-1} [a_{13ij} a_{21jj} \psi_i - a_{15jj} a_{13ij} \nabla^2 \psi_i \\
& - a_{3ij} (a_{2jj} a_{20jj} - a_{34jj} \nabla^2) (M_{ix} + M_{iy}) + a_{16jj} (a_{11ij} S_{4i} + a_{10ij} S_{5i})]
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{6j} &= \frac{\partial^2 M_{jx}^*}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{jxy}^*}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_{jy}^*}{\partial y^2} \\
S_{7j} &= \left(L_{4jj} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + L_{5jj} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) (S_{jx} - S_{jy}) \left(L_{5jj} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + L_{4jj} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) (S_{jy} - S_{jx}) \\
S_{8j} &= (a_{20jj} a_{30jj} + a_{35jj} \nabla^2) S_{3j} - (a_{2jj} a_{20jj} - a_{34jj} \nabla^2) (S_{3jx} + S_{3jy}) \\
& + a_{16jj} S_{7j} - S_{6j} + 0.5 a_{16jj} L_{15jj} L_{371j} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the equilibrium equations are divided into the two independent groups: the first one is for ψ_i , and the second one is for φ_i and w_i . The first group describes a vortical boundary layer, the second group, the internal stresses and potential boundary layer. The order of main equation is fourteen, and for the rest of equations is six. The functions of the previous conditions are included as known ones into the equations for the next conditions.

Using equation (46) we eliminate $\nabla^2 \psi_0$ from the equations (47) and (48), and then bring them to the governing equation by introducing a function Φ :

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi_* &= -a_{4611} \nabla^2 \Phi - 2a_{4211} \Phi \\
\psi_1 &= a_{4511} \nabla^2 \Phi + 2a_{4411} \Phi
\end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

Using (55) we arrive at the final equation

$$a_{4811} \nabla^4 \Phi + a_{4911} \nabla^2 \Phi + a_{5011} \Phi = 0 \tag{56}$$

This equation describes the vortical end effect as a first approximation.

Similarly, we obtain the equation for w_1 . Using equations (49) and (52) items $\nabla^2 \varphi_0$ and φ_1 can be excluded from (50). This equation will describe the internal stress state and the potential end effect of the first (non-balanced) stress state:

$$\begin{aligned}
(a_{7611} \nabla^6 + a_{8411} \nabla^4) w_1 &= a_{8211} q + a_{8511} \nabla^2 q \\
& + a_{8611} \nabla^4 q + a_{8711} \nabla^2 p + a_{8811} \nabla^4 p
\end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

When solving the bending problem of the plate of a non-symmetrical structure through the thickness the coefficients φ_0 and ψ_0 are expressed via u_0 and v_0 :

$$\begin{aligned}
& B \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v_0}{\partial x \partial y} \right) + 0.5 L_{1400} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 v_0}{\partial x \partial y} \right) + B_1 \frac{\partial \varphi_*}{\partial x} + 0.5 L_{1410} \frac{\partial \varphi_*}{\partial y} \\
& + L_{1810} \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x} + 0.5 L_{1510} \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial y} - 0.5 L_{2000} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + L_{2010} \frac{\partial q}{\partial x} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& B \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 v_0}{\partial y^2} \right) - 0.5 L_{1400} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial^2 v_0}{\partial x^2} \right) + B_1 \frac{\partial \varphi_*}{\partial y} - 0.5 L_{1410} \frac{\partial \varphi_*}{\partial x} \\
& + L_{1810} \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial y} - 0.5 L_{1510} \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial x} - 0.5 L_{2000} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + L_{2010} \frac{\partial q}{\partial y} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

Thus, the stress-strain state of the plate of non-symmetrical structure is described by the equations (56)-(59). The coefficients φ_* and φ_1 are determined with the help of w_1 and the external loads q and p using equations (49)-(52):

$$\begin{aligned}
\varphi_* &= -\nabla^2 w_1 - a_{7711}^{-1} [(a_{7611} - a_{8311} a_{7311}) \nabla^4 w_1 + (1 - a_{8311}) a_{7911} \nabla^2 q \\
&+ (a_{7111} - a_{8311}) q - 0.5 (a_{8011} - a_{8311} a_{7511}) \nabla^2 p]
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

$$\varphi_1 = a_{4211}^{-1} [q - a_{4111} (\nabla^2 w_1 + \varphi_*)] \tag{61}$$

The main unknowns in the displacement method are u_0 , v_0 , ψ_1 , ψ_* , φ_1 , φ_* and w_1 which are determined with the help of equations (56)-(59) and relations (55) and (60).

SOME RESULTS

Sinusoidal load

Let us consider a problem of bending of simply supported three-layered plate with non-symmetrical structure of the layer package subjected to a sinusoidal load. The plate can be geometrically non-symmetrical as well as have different material properties of the layers. The load is applied only to the top external surface and we assume that $0.5p = 0.5q$ and, therefore, the intensity of the load is given as

$$0.5p + 0.5q = q_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{l}$$

The components of the displacement w are determined at three points of each layer, at the top, middle and bottom of the layer. The following input data are used:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_3 E_2^{-1} &= 500, 10000; \quad E_3 E_1^{-1} = 100; \quad \nu_1 = \nu_2 = \nu_3 = 0.3 \\
lh^{-1} &= 5, 10; \quad t_2 t_1^{-1} = 1, 10; \quad t_2 t_3^{-1} = 1, 10
\end{aligned}$$

Here E_i , ν_i , t_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are elasticity moduli, Poisson's ratios and thicknesses of the layers; h is the total thickness of the plate, l is the dimension of the plate. The results are presented in the table below and compared with the exact solution obtained in [12]. The first three results are given for the top layer, next three for the middle layer, and last for the bottom layer. All the values were calculated at the centre of the plate.

As may be seen from the above tables, the results obtained using the proposed approach are in very good agreement with the exact solution.

The convergence and the accuracy of the solution obtained on the base of the free equations depend on the thickness of the plate and the differences between the material characteristics in different layers. The first approximation, i.e. initial model of the laminated plate, exerts the biggest influence on the speed of convergence. Even when analysing a significantly non-homogeneous plate it is enough to use only the first approximation of the theory. The equations for the next stress conditions should be mainly used in order to accurately analyse the end effects.

$\sigma_x^{(k)}(q_0)^{-1}$			$\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}(q_0)^{-1}$			$wE_1 \cdot 10^{-2}(q_0h)^{-1}$		
Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation	Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation	Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation
-64.72	-64.60	-64.61	0.000	0.000	0.000	6.325	6.337	6.333
-0.369	-0.373	-0.370	4.850	4.849	4.849	6.353	6.337	6.343
63.96	63.84	63.92	0.112	0.113	0.113	6.323	6.337	6.342
0.117	0.114	0.116	0.112	0.113	0.113	6.323	6.337	6.342
0.210	0.210	0.210	0.087	0.088	0.088	6.228	6.337	6.243
0.312	0.316	0.314	0.048	0.049	0.049	6.101	6.337	6.108
1.561	1.582	1.566	0.048	0.049	0.049	6.101	6.337	6.108
1.623	1.646	1.636	0.025	0.025	0.025	6.087	6.337	6.084
—	1.710	1.711	0.000	0.000	0.000	—	6.337	6.062

Table 1. Dimensionless stresses and displacements in the plate with $E_3E_1^{-1} = 100$, $E_3E_2^{-1} = 500$, $t_2t_1^{-1} = 10$, $t_2t_3^{-1} = 1$, $lh^{-1} = 5$.

$\sigma_x^{(k)}(q_0)^{-1}$			$\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}(q_0)^{-1}$			$wE_1 \cdot 10^{-2}(q_0h)^{-1}$		
Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation	Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation	Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation
-119.6	-113.9	-114.8	0.000	0.000	0.000	5.252	5.010	5.282
-65.45	-63.56	-63.58	1.385	1.508	1.418	5.252	5.010	5.265
-11.25	-13.22	-12.49	1.958	1.926	1.941	5.253	5.010	5.277
-0.434	-0.439	-0.438	1.958	1.926	1.941	5.253	5.010	5.277
-0.077	-0.099	-0.091	1.996	1.924	1.953	5.177	5.010	5.140
0.262	0.259	0.263	1.982	1.923	1.935	5.117	5.010	5.134
1.938	1.873	1.894	1.982	1.923	1.935	5.117	5.010	5.134
6.578	6.400	6.384	1.348	1.447	1.437	5.072	5.010	5.022
11.50	11.24	11.27	0.000	0.000	0.000	4.988	5.010	4.982

Table 2. Dimensionless stresses and displacements in the plate with $E_3E_1^{-1} = 100$, $E_3E_2^{-1} = 500$, $t_2t_1^{-1} = 1$, $t_2t_3^{-1} = 10$, $lh^{-1} = 5$.

$\sigma_x^{(k)}(q_0)^{-1}$			$\sigma_{xz}^{(k)}(q_0)^{-1}$			$wE_1 \cdot 10^{-2}(q_0h)^{-1}$		
Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation	Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation	Exact so- lution	First approx- imation	Second approx- imation
-770.7	-758.3	-759.7	0.000	0.000	0.000	2125	2094	2109
-221.8	-220.3	-220.3	3.712	3.748	3.669	2125	2094	2109
326.9	317.6	318.9	3.319	3.320	3.319	2125	2094	2109
-0.376	-0.382	-0.382	3.319	3.320	3.319	2125	2094	2109
-0.435	-0.419	-0.419	3.349	3.324	3.324	2110	2094	2109
-0.502	-0.456	-0.456	3.384	3.342	3.343	2102	2094	2109
-31.03	-30.93	-30.89	3.384	3.342	3.343	2102	2094	2109
22.57	22.41	22.39	3.700	3.744	3.703	2103	2094	2109
76.44	76.03	76.06	0.000	0.000	0.000	2098	2094	2086

Table 3. Dimensionless stresses and displacements in the plate with $E_3E_1^{-1} = 100$, $E_3E_2^{-1} = 10000$, $t_2t_1^{-1} = 1$, $t_2t_3^{-1} = 10$, $lh^{-1} = 10$.

Arbitrarily distributed pressure

Now let us consider a simply supported transversely isotropic rectangular plate with dimensions $a \times b$, subjected to an arbitrarily distributed pressure $p(x, y) = q(x, y)$ over the top external surface. In order to determine the stress state in the plate we shall be using the equations (57)–(59) and (54), for the solution of which the Navier method is used. It should be noted that this problem does not have any vortical end effect and, thus, the equations (56) and (53) become equalities.

For the solution of the problem in the first approximation we use the displacement method in combination with the force method, whereas, for the subsequent approximations only the displacement method is used.

The following boundary conditions correspond to the simply supported edges of the plate:

— for the nonself-balanced stress state ($x = 0, a$)

$$v_0 = v_1 = v_* = w_1 = N_x = M_{1x} = \tilde{M}_{1x} = 0 \quad (x \rightarrow y, u \leftarrow v) \quad (62)$$

— for self-balanced ($i \geq 2$) states ($x = 0, a$)

$$L_{1jj}M_{jx} - M_{jx}^* = v_j = w_j = 0 \quad (x \rightarrow y, v \rightarrow u) \quad (63)$$

The load applied to the top external surface can be expanded in the following series

$$q(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_{mn} S_x S_y \quad (64)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} S_x &= \sin(p_m x); & S_y &= \sin(p_n y) \\ p_m &= m\pi a^{-1}; & p_n &= n\pi b^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

The end conditions (62) and (63) will be satisfied if the solution of (57)–(59) and (54) will be given as

$$\begin{aligned} w_i &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_{imn} S_x S_y; & F &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} F_{mn} S_x S_y \\ \varphi_* &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \varphi_{*mn} S_x S_y; & \varphi_i &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \varphi_{imn} S_x S_y \\ u_0 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_{0mn} C_x S_y; & v_0 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_{0mn} S_x C_y \\ Q_{ix} &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Q_{ixmn} C_x S_y \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y); & M_{ix} &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} M_{ixmn} S_x S_y \quad (x \rightleftharpoons y) \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

where

$$C_x = \cos(p_m x); \quad C_y = \cos(p_n y) \quad (67)$$

Substituting (66) into (57)–(59) and (54) and comparing the coefficients of the same harmonics we obtain an algebraic system of equations for the constant coefficients in (66).

As an example we solved a problem where the external transverse load (64) was expressed by only one term of the series ($m = n = 1$)

$$q = q_{11}S_xS_y \quad (68)$$

The following material characteristics were used:

$$E_1E_2^{-1} = 10^3; \nu_1 = \nu_2 = \nu_3 = 0.3; ah^{-1} = 5, 10, 20, 40; t_2t_1^{-1} = 0.6, 8$$

After the two approximations the solution of the square ($a \times a$) sandwich plate of the symmetrical structure was compared with that obtained in [13].

The results presented in the table below are given for the displacement w of the middle surface and the stresses $\sigma_x^{(k)}$ at the point $z = 0.5h$, located at the centre of the plate. A good conformity of the approximate solutions confirms the trustworthiness of the obtained results. The discrepancy between the two solutions becomes less pronounced with the decrease in the relative thickness of the plate.

ah^{-1}	$t_2t_1^{-1} = 8$				$t_2t_1^{-1} = 0.6$			
	$\max w E_1 (10^4 q_0 h)^{-1}$		$\max \sigma_x (q_0)^{-1}$		$\max w E_1 (10^4 q_0 h)^{-1}$		$\max \sigma_x (q_0)^{-1}$	
	[13]	Present	[13]	Present	[13]	Present	[13]	Present
5	0.257	0.237	78.60	68.90	–	0.125	–	15.68
10	1.260	1.238	121.0	120.2	0.194	0.191	55.80	54.38
20	5.960	5.962	247.0	247.6	1.920	1.919	159.0	158.4
40	35.23	35.20	733.0	734.3	15.40	15.79	434.0	431.1

Table 4. Bending of a simply supported sandwich plate of the symmetrical structure subjected to sinusoidal load.

Locally distributed pressure

The pressure can also be distributed locally, on the area less than the surface area of the plate. The simplest case is uniformly distributed load over a square area. For the solution of this problem we use the Navier method, and if the load intensity is q_0 , then the coefficients of the series (64) are calculated as

$$q_{mn} = \frac{16q_0}{\pi^2 mn} \sin \frac{m\pi\xi}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi\eta}{b} \sin \frac{m\pi a_0}{2a} \sin \frac{n\pi b_0}{2b} \quad (69)$$

where a_0 and b_0 are dimensions of the square area occupied by the local load along the axes x and y , respectively; η and ξ are the distances from the centre of gravity of the load area to the axes x and y .

The conducted study showed that the displacements and stresses, due to the locally distributed pressure, are already well described after the first approximation. The change in the ratio $E_1E_2^{-1}$ does not influence significantly the corrections of the second approximation.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

The present study presents a new iterative theory based on a variational approach for the analysis of significantly non-homogeneous laminated plates of unsymmetrical structure.

The governing equations are of practical interest in the analysis and design of the plates. In addition, the study shows a new development of variational methods as applied to the analysis of significantly inhomogeneous layered plates of unsymmetrical structure through the thickness.

For the first iteration, the approximation functions for stresses and strains, which take more fully into account the deformation characteristics of such plates, are used. The iterative theory, which takes into account all the components of the stress and strain state, and simultaneously, describes both the internal stress state and the end effect of the boundary layer, is derived. This guarantees a more accurate account of the boundary conditions. The accuracy and practical convergence of the solution on the basis of the proposed iterative theory is studied.

The derived refined theory of significantly heterogeneous laminated plates allows us, with a required accuracy and without major difficulties, to obtain solutions for different plate deformation problems, including those problems showing an extreme change in the stress state. It is also important that, with an increase in the accuracy of the solution, the order of the equations for the series of self-balanced stressed conditions remains constant and thus significantly simplifies solutions with a high number of iterations. Analytical solutions are obtained for the bending problem of a simply supported plate subject to various load conditions including locally distributed forces.

The results of the analysed plates demonstrate a very good convergence of the solution and the results obtained are in a very good agreement when compared with those in the literature. Besides, the derived theory can form a basis for designing a new finite element for the analysis of the above class of problems.

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APPENDIX A

$$L_{1ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \int_{t_k} f_i f_j dz;$$

$$L_{3ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \frac{d\alpha_i^{(k)}}{dz} \frac{df_i}{dz} dz;$$

$$L_{5ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu^{(k)} E_0^{(k)}}{D_1^2 (1 - \nu_k^2)} \int_{t_k} f_i f_j dz;$$

$$L_{7ij} = L_{4ij} + L_{5ij};$$

$$L_{9ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} \alpha_i \alpha_j dz;$$

$$L_{11ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \frac{df_i}{dz} \frac{d\alpha_j}{dz};$$

$$L_{13ij} = L_{4ij} - L_{5ij};$$

$$L_{14ij} = D_1 - L_{17ij};$$

$$L_{16ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} (1 - \nu_k) \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} \alpha_j^{(k)} dz;$$

$$L_{18ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz;$$

$$L_{20ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} (1 + \nu^{(k)}) \int_{t_k} \alpha_i^{(k)} f_j dz;$$

$$L_{22ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} \frac{df_j}{dz} dz;$$

$$L_{24ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} \frac{df_1}{dz} \frac{df_j}{dz};$$

$$L_{26ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{E_k} \frac{(E_0^{(k)})^2}{D_1} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz;$$

$$L_{28ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{(E_0^{(k)})^2 \nu_3^{(k)} (1 + \nu^{(k)})}{E^{(k)} D_1 E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} \alpha_i f_j dz;$$

$$L_{2ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \alpha_i^{(k)} \frac{d^2 f_i}{dz} dz$$

$$L_{4ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1^2 (1 - \nu_k^2)} \int_{t_k} f_i f_j dz$$

$$L_{6ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_3^{(k)} E_0^{(k)}}{D_1 E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} \alpha_i f_j dz;$$

$$L_{8ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \frac{d^2 f_i}{dz} \alpha_j^{(k)} dz$$

$$L_{10ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_3^{(k)} E_0^{(k)}}{D_1 E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} f_i \alpha_j dz;$$

$$L_{12ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{G_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} \frac{d\alpha_i^{(k)}}{dz} \frac{d\alpha_j^{(k)}}{dz} dz$$

$$L_{14ij} = B_j - L_{17ij}$$

$$L_{15ij} = L_{18ij} - L_{19ij}$$

$$L_{17ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \mu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} f_i f_j dz$$

$$L_{19ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \nu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz$$

$$L_{21ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \nu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} f_i \frac{df_j}{dz} dz$$

$$L_{23ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \nu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} \frac{df_j}{dz} dz$$

$$L_{25ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} (1 + \nu^{(k)}) \int_{t_k} \alpha_i^{(k)} \frac{df_j}{dz} dz$$

$$L_{27ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu^{(k)} (E_0^{(k)})^2}{E^{(k)} D_1} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz$$

$$L_{29ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_k^2 (E_0^{(k)})^2}{E^{(k)} D_1} \int_{t_k} f_i f_j dz$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L_{301j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu^{(k)}(E_0^{(k)})^2}{E^{(k)}D_1} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz; & L_{311j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_k^2(E_0^{(k)})^2}{E^{(k)}D_1} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz \\
L_{32ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu^{(k)}(E_0^{(k)})^2 \nu_3^{(k)}(1 + \nu^{(k)})}{E^{(k)}D_1 E_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} \alpha_i f_j dz; & L_{33ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} E_0^{(k)} \nu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} f_i \alpha_j dz \\
L_{341j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} \alpha_j^{(k)} dz; & L_{351j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\nu_3^{(k)}}{E_3^{(k)}} E_0^{(k)} \nu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} \alpha_j dz \\
L_{36ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \frac{(\nu_3^{(k)})^2}{(E_3^{(k)})^2} (1 + \nu^{(k)}) \int_{t_k} \alpha_i^{(k)} \alpha_j^{(k)} dz; & L_{371j} &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{E_0^{(k)}}{D_1} \int_{t_k} R^{(k)} f_j dz \\
L_{381j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} \frac{dR^{(k)}}{dz} \frac{d\alpha_j^{(k)}}{dz} dz; & L_{3911} &= \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \int_{t_k} (R^{(k)})^2 dz \\
L_{4011} &= \sum_{k=1}^m E_0^{(k)} \nu^{(k)} \int_{t_k} (R^{(k)})^2 dz; & L_{4111} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} f_*^{(k)} \frac{df_j}{dz} dz \\
L_{4211} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \int_{t_k} f_* \frac{dR^{(k)}}{dz} dz; & L_{4311} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{G_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} (f_*^{(k)})^2 dz \\
L_{441j} &= \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{G_3^{(k)}} \int_{t_k} f_*^{(k)} \frac{d\alpha_j^{(k)}}{dz} dz; & L_{4511} &= L_{3911} - L_{4011} \\
L_{46ij} &= L_{18ij} - L_{19ij}; \quad f_0 = 1; & \alpha_0 &= 1; \quad f_1 = z
\end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX B

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{1jj} &= L_{9jj}L_{13jj} - 2L_{6jj}L_{10jj}; \\
a_{3ij} &= L_{10ij} - L_{13ij}L_{10jj}/L_{13jj}; \\
a_{5jj} &= (L_{1jj}L_{2jj}L_{10jj}L_{12jj} \\
&\quad - a_{1jj}L_{13jj}L_{11jj})/a_{1jj}/L_{12jj}; \\
a_{7ij} &= L_{6ij} - L_{6jj}L_{13ij}a_{12ij}/a_{1jj}; \\
a_{9ij} &= L_{3ij} - L_{3jj}L_{12ij}/L_{12jj}; \\
a_{11ij} &= L_{4ij}L_{4jj} - L_{5ij}L_{5jj}; \\
a_{13ij} &= L_{3jj}L_{11ij}/L_{12jj}; \\
a_{15jj} &= L_{1jj}^2 a_{6jj}/a_{5jj}L_{13jj}; \\
a_{17ij} &= a_{2jj}a_{15jj}L_{8ij} + a_{20jj}a_{13ij} - a_{8ij}; \\
a_{19ij} &= a_{3ij}(a_{2jj}a_{15jj} - L_{1jj}L_{6jj}/a_{1jj}); \\
a_{21ij} &= a_{20ij} + 1; \\
a_{23ij} &= a_{9ij}a_{22ij}; \\
a_{251j} &= L_{411j} - L_{3jj}L_{441j}/L_{12jj}; \\
a_{27jj} &= L_{6jj}L_{7jj}L_{13jj}/a_{1jj}; \\
a_{291j} &= L_{1jj}L_{381j}/L_{12jj} - L_{2jj}L_{10jj}L_{181j}/a_{1jj}/D_1; \\
a_{311j} &= L_{1jj}L_{181j}a_{6jj}/L_{13jj}/D_1; \\
a_{331j} &= a_{20jj}a_{291j} + a_{261j}; \\
a_{35jj} &= a_{16jj}a_{28jj} - a_{15jj}a_{30jj}; \\
a_{3711} &= L_{3811}L_{4311} - L_{4211}L_{4411}; \\
a_{3911} &= L_{3811}L_{4411} - L_{4211}L_{1211}; \\
a_{4111} &= (L_{4111}a_{3811} - L_{311}a_{3611})/a_{4011}; \\
a_{4311} &= (L_{4211}a_{3811} - L_{3811}a_{3611})/a_{4011}; \\
a_{4511} &= L_{1411} - L_{1410}^2/L_{1400}; \\
a_{4711} &= L_{4511} - L_{1510}^2/L_{1400}; \\
a_{4911} &= 2(a_{4711}a_{4111} + a_{4411}a_{4511} \\
&\quad - a_{4611}a_{4211} - a_{4611}a_{4311}); \\
a_{5111} &= a_{4211}a_{4311} - a_{4411}a_{4111}; \\
a_{5311} &= D_1a_{4411} - L_{1811}a_{4211}; \\
a_{551j} &= L_{201j}a_{4411} - L_{161j}a_{4211}; \\
a_{5711} &= D_1a_{4311} - L_{1811}a_{4111}; \\
a_{591j} &= L_{201j}a_{4311} - L_{161j}a_{4111}; \\
a_{6111} &= L_{1411}a_{4411} - L_{1511}a_{4211}; \\
a_{6311} &= L_{1410}a_{4311} - L_{1510}a_{4111}; \\
a_{6511} &= L_{1511}a_{4311} - L_{4511}a_{4111}; \\
a_{6710} &= B_1/B; \\
a_{6910} &= L_{1810}/B; \\
a_{2jj} &= L_{2jj}L_{13jj}/a_{1jj} \\
a_{4ij} &= L_{2ij} - a_{2jj}a_{12ij} \\
a_{6jj} &= L_{4jj}/L_{7jj} + L_{6jj}L_{10jj}/a_{1jj} \\
a_{8ij} &= L_{1jj}L_{6jj}L_{8ij}/a_{1jj} - a_{13ij} \\
a_{10ij} &= L_{4ij}L_{5jj} - L_{4jj}L_{5ij} \\
a_{12ij} &= L_{9ij} - 2L_{6ij}L_{10jj}/L_{13jj} \\
a_{14jj} &= a_{2jj}a_{20jj} \\
a_{16jj} &= L_{1jj}/L_{7jj}/L_{13jj} \\
a_{18ij} &= a_{4ij}a_{15jj} - L_{1jj}a_{7ij}/L_{13jj} \\
a_{20ij} &= a_{13ij}/a_{5jj} \\
a_{22ij} &= 2L_{7ij}/L_{1jj}^2 \\
a_{24ij} &= a_{13ij}a_{22ij} \\
a_{26ij} &= L_{3jj}L_{381j}/L_{12jj} \\
a_{28jj} &= L_{6jj}L_{7jj}L_{10jj}/a_{1jj} \\
a_{30jj} &= L_{2jj}L_{10jj}/a_{1jj} \\
a_{321j} &= a_{15jj}a_{291j} + a_{311j} \\
a_{34jj} &= a_{15jj}a_{2jj} - a_{16jj}a_{27jj} \\
a_{3611} &= L_{1111}L_{4311} - L_{4111}L_{4411} \\
a_{3811} &= L_{1111}L_{4411} - L_{4111}L_{1211} \\
a_{4011} &= L_{1211}L_{4311} - L_{4411}^2 \\
a_{4211} &= (L_{4111}a_{3911} - L_{311}a_{3711})/a_{4011} \\
a_{4411} &= (L_{4211}a_{3911} - L_{3811}a_{3711})/a_{4011} \\
a_{4611} &= L_{1511} - L_{1510}L_{1410}/L_{1400} \\
a_{4811} &= a_{4711}a_{4511} - a_{4611}^2 \\
a_{5011} &= 4(a_{4411}a_{4111} - a_{4311}a_{4211}) \\
a_{5211} &= B_1a_{4411} - L_{1810}a_{4211} \\
a_{5411} &= L_{1811}a_{4411} - L_{3911}a_{4211} \\
a_{5611} &= B_1a_{4311} - L_{1810}a_{4111} \\
a_{5811} &= L_{1811}a_{4311} - L_{3911}a_{4111} \\
a_{6011} &= L_{1410}a_{4411} - L_{1510}a_{4211} \\
a_{6211} &= L_{1511}a_{4411} - L_{4511}a_{4211} \\
a_{6411} &= L_{1411}a_{4311} - L_{1511}a_{4111} \\
a_{661j} &= L_{181j}a_{4111}/a_{4211} \\
a_{681j} &= L_{181j}/a_{4211} \\
a_{7011} &= L_{3911}/a_{4211}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{7111} &= a_{4411}/a_{4211}; & a_{7211} &= D_1 - a_{6710}(B_1 - a_{6610}) - a_{6611} \\
a_{7311} &= a_{6710}a_{6610} - a_{6611}; & a_{7411} &= L_{2011} - a_{6710}(L_{2010} + a_{6810}) + a_{6811} \\
a_{7511} &= L_{2010} - a_{6710}L_{2000}; & a_{7611} &= a_{6910}a_{6610} - a_{4111}a_{7011} \\
a_{7711} &= a_{4311} - a_{7111}a_{4111}; & a_{7811} &= L_{1811} - a_{6910}(B - a_{6610}) - a_{7011}a_{4111} \\
a_{7911} &= L_{1611} - a_{6910}(L_{2010} + a_{6810}) & & \\
&+ L_{3911}/a_{4211}; & a_{8011} &= L_{1610} - a_{6910}L_{2000} \\
a_{8111} &= a_{7311}/a_{7211}; & a_{8211} &= a_{7711}/a_{7211} \\
a_{8311} &= a_{7811}/a_{7211}; & a_{8411} &= a_{7711}(1 - a_{8111}) - a_{7811}a_{8111} \\
a_{8511} &= a_{8211}a_{7411} + a_{8311} - a_{7111}; & a_{8611} &= a_{8311}a_{7411} - a_{7911} \\
a_{8711} &= a_{8211}a_{7511}/2; & a_{8811} &= (a_{8311}a_{7511} - a_{8011})/2
\end{aligned}$$